

This was noted experimentally. Due to inhomogeneous excitation photo voltage produced decomposes water⁶.

Due to photo electric current and decomposition of H₂O the corrosion rate increases in presence of white light (Fig. 1). It has also been reported that Cu/CuCl electrode is affected by light in solution. The potential tends to more negative value when it is exposed to light⁷. Moreover photo solvation and photo decomposition of solvated complex has been suggested.⁸

These photochemical reactions at the Cu/CuCl electrode surface may be responsible for increased corrosion in presence of white light. Due to the anomalous photovoltages and micro semiconductor film junction photo diffusion processes are also going on⁹. Photo diffusion of Cu⁺ ions between the inner metal surface and the porous CuCl film in presence of white light is also one of the causes for increased corrosion in presence of sunlight.

Conclusion

In conclusion the investigation has shown that corrosion of α -brass in aqueous solutions of hydrochloric acid as well as of sodium chloride increases in presence of light which is due to the semiconducting photosensitive film of CuCl formed on the plate surface as a product of corrosion. Photocorrosion of brass in aqueous hydrochloric acid and sodium chloride solutions is proportional to the concentration of the solution.

References

1. YU. M. KOROVIN and I. B. ULANOVSKII., *Zashch Metal.*, 1971, 7, 312 as per *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, 75, 83923.
2. I. SEKERKA, K. SMREEK, S. VURLICEK and K. BERANEK., *Chem. Listy.*, 1958, 52, 1218 as per *Chem. Abs.*, 1959, 53, 174g.
3. F. A. CHAMPION., 'Corrosion Testing Procedures'. Chapman and Hall, London. 1952, p. 187.
4. J. FRANCO and N. K. PATEL., *Denki Kagaku J. of electrochem. Soc., Japan*, 1973, 41, 670.
5. NAKANESHI, SHIGEMITSU and KAUFU YORO., *J. Phys. Soc. Japan*, 1968, 25, 1330.
6. H. P. KALLMANN and M. PAPE., *Nature*, 1960, 188, 935.
7. M. POURBAIX, P. MUYLDER J. AND VAN LEAR, *Corros. Sci.*, 1967, 7, 795.
8. J. FRANCO and N. K. PATEL, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1973, 47, 571.
9. E. I. ADIROVICH, T. MIRZAMAKHMUDOV and H. YU. M. YUABOV., *Izv. Akad. Nauk. Uzb. SSR. Fiz. Mat. Nauk.*, 1971, 15, 36 as per *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, 75, 2678.

Direct Titrimetric Microdetermination of Mercury (II). Simultaneous Determination of Mercury (II) and Lead

J. V. G. KRISHNAMURTHY

Department of Chemistry, P. S. G. College of Technology, Coimbatore-4.

&

O. C. SAXENA

Chemistry Department, Allahabad University, Allahabad.

Manuscript received 30 January 1974; accepted 23 May 1974

THE literature is not rich in methods for the direct determination of mercury (II) or the simultaneous determination of its mixture with lead. However, mercury (II) has been determined volumetrically with

KCNs using diphenyl carbazone (1), with CDTA (1), by titrating with EDTA (7), with TBA (8), and by reduction and then oxidizing mercury (II) (10); colorimetrically using titan yellow (2); fluorometrically using Rhodamine-s(3); by chelation (8); by reacting with 3-hydroxochromone (5); and by electrometric titrations (6). The present work deals with the determination of mercury (II) in microamounts by directly titrating its ions in the hippuric acid, using bromocresol green as indicator. Potentiometric titrations and results of analysis show that the complex between mercury (II) and hippuric acid is formed in the ratio of 1:2. Probably the following reaction takes place :

Similar is the case with Lead (II)

Experimental

Reagents : Hippuric acid (E. Merk grade), mercuric chloride and lead nitrate (Analar B. D. H. grade), Xylenol orange and bromocresol green (B. D. H. grade) were used without further purification.

Apparatus used : 1/100 graded micro pipette and micro burette were employed. Standard mercuric chloride and silver nitrate solutions were prepared by dissolving the exactly weighed amount in distilled water. Xylenol orange and bromocresol green solutions were prepared by dissolving 0.1g with 100 ml distilled water. Standard hippuric acid solution was prepared by dissolving the exactly weighed amount in hot distilled water.

A. Procedure for mercury (II) : Pipetted a known volume of a standard mercury (II) solution into a beaker, diluted with distilled water to 30 ml and added 2-3 drops of bromocresol green. Titrated the green coloured solution with standard hippuric acid solution to the first sharp colour change to the oil of winter green.

B. Procedure for the simultaneous determination of Lead and Mercury(II) : Pipetted known volumes of lead and mercury (II) solutions into the titration beaker and diluted to 30 ml by adding distilled water. Added 2-3 drops of Xylenol orange. Titrated the pink coloured solution with standard hippuric acid solution to the first sharp colour change to pale yellow. To the same solution added bromocresol green and determined mercury (II) following (A).

Results and Discussion

Results are given in Table 1 and 2. Lead and Mercury (II) determinations covered the ranges from 0.4127 to 1.0320 mg and from 0.3996 to 0.9990 mg with maximum errors 0.6% and 0.5% respectively.

TABLE 1. MICRO DETERMINATION OF MERCURY (II).

Mercuric chloride (ml)	Hippuric acid (ml)	Mercury (mg)		error %
		taken	found	
0.01M	0.0249M			
0.2	0.16	0.4012	0.3996	0.4
0.3	0.24	0.6017	0.5990	0.5
0.4	0.32	0.8024	0.7990	0.4
0.5	0.40	1.0030	0.9990	0.4

TABLE 2. SIMULTANEOUS MICRODETERMINATION OF LEAD AND MERCURY(II)

Pb (No ₃) ₂ (ml)	Hippuric acid (ml) taken	Lead (mg) found	Mercuric chloride	Hippuric acid (ml) taken	Mercury (mg) found
0.01M	0.0249M		0.01M	0.249M	
0.2	0.16	0.4144	0.5	0.40	0.3996
0.3	0.24	0.6230	0.4	0.32	0.5990
0.4	0.32	0.8288	0.3	0.24	0.7990
0.5	0.40	1.0360	0.2	0.16	0.9990

In Table 2, lead and mercury (II) have been titrated together in the ascending order from the top; while making calculations for lead and mercury (II), the observed values have been divided by 2, since the complex between lead and hippuric acid or mercury (II) and hippuric acid takes place in the ratio 1:2.

It has been observed that the complexes between lead or mercury and hippuric acid are formed at p^H 6.1 and 5.2 respectively.

The present method is direct, simple and very much less time consuming than other methods, already described.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to C.S.I.R. for providing financial assistance. One of the authors (J.V.G.K.) is grateful to the management of P. S. G. College of Technology for the encouragement in this work.

References

1. E. HOFFMANN and A. SARACZ., *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1963, 199, 6.
2. D. NEGGIN and A. KRIZ., *Anolele Univ. "C. I. PARHON" Bucuresh. Ser. Stiint. Naf. Chem.* 1962, 1135, 117.
3. A. I. IVANKOVA., D. N. PRINOVA and D. P. SHCHERBOV., *Prom. Khis. Reaktivov osobo chist. Veshchestre.* 1967, 8, 174.
4. H. KHALIFA., *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1964, 203, 151.
5. A. MURATA, H. TAKUSHI, K. FUJIYASU and T. SUZUKI., *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1966, 13, 143.
6. G. G. BOMBI and M. FIORAM., *Talanta*, 1965, 12, 1053.
7. G. K. SINGHAL and K. N. TANDON., *Talanta*, 1967, 14, 1351.
8. J. CHWASTOWSKA., *Proc. Conf. Appl. Phys. Chem. methods. Chem. Anal. Budapest*, 1966, 1, 45.
9. L. M. ANDREASOV, E. I. VAIL, V. A. KREMER, Z. N. CHERNYAeva and S. A. REZNICHENKE., *IZU. Vysh. Vchev. Zaved. Khim Khim Tekhnol.*, 1967, 10, 743.
10. O. C. SAXENA., *Mikrochim. Acta.* 1967, 1123.
11. J. V. G. KRISHNAMURTHY., and O. C. SAXENA., *U.A.R.J. chem.* 1970, 13, 375.

Some Aspects on the Isolation of UCl₄·2Ph₂SO·2H₂O and a Study of its Electronic Spectra and Magnetic Susceptibility

A. K. MAJUMDAR and R. G. BHATTACHARYYA

Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700032

Manuscript received 19 September 1973; revised 17 May 1974; accepted 23 May 1974

IN a previous communication¹ it was pointed out that the title compound could only be isolated provided the reactants, UCl₄ and Ph₂SO are mixed in a mole proportion less than 1 : 2. Some further precautionary measures, which are essential for the isolation of the above compound are being outlined here.

1. The hydrochloric acid solution of UO₂Cl₂ prepared from U₃O₈ should not be evaporated upto extremely dry condition; this slightly moist residue should be taken up with ether for reduction with zinc and hydrogen chloride.

2. It was found preferable to use small amount of zinc granules and to allow more time for the completion of the reduction process than to use excess zinc dust to accelerate the rate of reduction. Use of excess zinc dust leads to deposition of UCl₄ on it, thereby modifying the UCl₄ : Ph₂SO ratio, resulting in the deposition of UCl₄ · 2Ph₂SO.

The compound shows 2: 1 electrolytic behaviour in methanol² and so it is presumed that the complex species undergoes solvolytic reactions³⁻⁵ in the above solvent. The substance behaves as a weak electrolyte in acetonitrile and the ionisation is far less evidenced from the very low conductance value (Ca 20 Ohm⁻¹ Cm²) at Ca 10⁻²M solution; and so a 2.20 x 10⁻² molar solution (nearly a saturated solution) of the substance in acetonitrile has been considered suitable for the measurement of the electronic spectra (in the visible region) as no other non-interacting solvent is capable of keeping the compound in solution. The visible band (25-10k) with their likely origins are given in the table. It was not possible to record the f transitions in the spectra of this substance in the long wavelength range for want of a suitable instrument.

TABLE—THE OPTICAL SPECTRAL BANDS OF UCl₄·2Ph₂SO·2H₂O IN ACETONITRILE AND THEIR LIKELY ORIGINS.

Terminal level	Band positions (Cm ⁻¹)	ε _{max}
3F ₃ , 3F ₄	10,870 - 12,200	4.10 for 10870 Cm ⁻¹ band (others are broad shoulders)
3H ₆	14,710; 15,270	25.2; 19.5
1D ₂	16,670 (Sh)	—
3P ₁	17,860	7.7
1I ₆	20,240; 21,550	10.9; 8.9; 13.4
	22,470	
3P ₂	23,040	11.8

Assuming the 5f² configuration for U(IV) ion, the bands in the spectra are assigned⁶ to transitions from the ground state ³H₄ to other levels within the configuration 5f² (the table). The overall energy span of the levels within the configuration depends on: (1) ligand field, (2) extent of inter electronic repulsion and (3) spin orbit coupling interactions⁷. So, the additional splitting of the bands observed is due to the elimination of (2J+1) fold degeneracy of the individual levels. This may be due to significant interaction with the ligand field.